

EFFECT OF FERTIGATION LEVELS ON HYBRID TOMATO PRODUCTION

P. B. Jadhav, M. U. Kale, M. S. Supe, R. S. Talole

Department of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering,

Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola

supemital@gmail.com

MS Received: 25.05.2024; MS Revised:30.06.2024; MS Accepted:01.07.2024)

MS 3220

(RESEARCH PAPER IN IRRIGATION AND DRAINAGE ENGINEERING,,)

Abstract

An experiment was conducted during rabi season of 2023-24 to study effects of fertigation levels on hybrid tomato production at instructional Farm of Department of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola. It was observed that drip fertigation with 120% of RDF resulted in highest yield with water use efficiency as 0.27 q/ha-mm.

Keywords: Tomato, Fertigation, RDF, Drip, WUE

Introduction

Water is an invaluable natural resource, essential to all life, and a vital national resource. The conditions for life on Earth are changing due to the rapid growth of human civilization and scientific and technological breakthroughs. Unrelenting population increase necessitates careful planning and management of the finite water resources due to the ensuing spike in water demand. The population of India is increasing by about 2% a year. Food production needs to increase by about 2.5% per year in order to guarantee better food consumption (Michael, 1974). Utilizing the limited water resources needs to be appropriately prioritized in order to be fully utilized and optimized. The long-term perspective planning of water resources is required to achieve the goals of economic growth and quality of life in a sustainable manner.

Agriculture is a significant driver of our economy, accounting for 14% of the GDP and roughly 11% of exports. India has the largest gross irrigated area (IWP) and is the world's largest user of groundwater. The country receives 1200 mm of rain on average per year. India's population is expected to reach 1.6 billion people by 2050, which will raise the nation's needs for energy, water, and food. India would face severe water shortages by 2050.

Tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicum*), is one of the popular solanaceous vegetable crops being grown widely in India. It occupies prime place amongst the vegetables. It is one of the most highly priced vegetables consumed salad as well as curry. Tomato otherwise called as 'Love apple' or Golden apple' or 'Poor man's apple' is one, which has attained worldwide importance. It is a good source of vitamin A, C and potassium. Lycopene pigment imparts red color and is a potential anti-oxidant for minimizing the damage caused by free radicals (Ayyar, 2019). The leading tomato growing states are, Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Orissa, and West Bengal.

Tomato is one of the most widely grown vegetable crops in the world and it is reported to be a heavy feeder of fertilizers. Since irrigation and fertilization are intrinsically linked, appropriate irrigation management is required for tomato grown on all types of soils in order to avoid nutrient leaching and groundwater pollution. This is more important especially in tomato production systems, which require substantial inputs of nitrogen fertilizer in addition, yields of large and total tomato fruits increased with drip applied N and K compared to pre-plant application. Similar to frequent application of water, split applications of fertilizer through fertigation improves quality and quantity of tomatoes over conventional practice.

India is the third fertilizer producing and consuming country in the world. The nutrient consumption per hectare and fertilizer use efficiency is very low in India. The main reasons for low efficiency are the type of fertilizer used and its method of application adopted by Indian farmers. Hence, there is a need to develop a suitable method of application of fertilizer, which will improve the quantity and quality of crop production. Fertigation is the process of application of water-soluble solid fertilizers or liquid fertilizers through drip irrigation system. Through fertigation, nutrients are applied directly into the wetted volume of soil immediately below the emitter, where root activity is concentrated (Ayyar, 2019).

Drip fertigation in combination with mulch is one of the best management options, which can improve the water management practice significantly. The advantages of mulching in vegetable crop production have been well documented. Mulch is simply a protective layer of a material that is spread on top of the soil. It enriches and protects soil and provides a better growing environment. At the same time, it acts as barrier to movement of moisture out of the soil. Mulches can effectively minimize water vapour loss, soil erosion, weed problems and nutrient loss. Mulching reduces the deterioration of soil, minimizes the weed infestation, provide micro climate for proper root growth and checks the water evaporation. The plastic materials used as mulch are polyvinyl chloride or polyethylene films. Polyethylene mulch is preferred as mulching material for crop production.

An experiment was conducted during rabi season of 2023-24 to study effects of fertigation levels on hybrid tomato production at instructional Farm of Department of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola.

Material and Methods**Climate at experimental site**

Akola lies between North latitudes 20°16' and 21°17' and; East longitudes 76°38' and 77°38'. Average annual rainfall ranges from 740 mm to 860 mm. The climate of Akola is subtropical semi-arid characterized by three different seasons namely summer becoming hot and dry from March to May, the warm and rainy monsoon from June to October and winter with mild cold from November to February. The average minimum temperature is 12.6 °C and mean maximum temperature is 42.4 °C.

Details of experimentation**Experimental design and treatments**

The field experiment was framed in randomized block design, with five treatments and four replications; of which details are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Treatment details

Treatments	Specification
T ₁	Drip fertigation with 60% of RDF
T ₂	Drip fertigation with 80% of RDF
T ₃	Drip fertigation with 100% of RDF
T ₄	Drip fertigation with 120% of RDF

T₅	Traditional application of fertilizer with 100% RDF (Soil application of basal dose of 50% N + 100% P + 100% through solid fertilizers at the time of transplanting and remaining 50% N in two equal splits at 30 and 45 days after transplanting) – Control
----------------------	--

Experimental Details

The details of experiment are given below.

Table 3.4. Experimental Details

Sr. No.	Particulars	Specifications
1.	Crop	Tomato (Hybrid)
2.	Scientific name	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>
3.	Variety	Syngenta Saaho
4.	Experimental Design	Randomized Block Design
5.	Number of treatments	5
6.	Number of replications	4
7.	Number of plots	20
8.	Plot size	1.2 m × 15.7 m
9.	Season	Rabi
10.	Crop spacing	0.90 m X 0.60 m
11.	Crop period	120 - 160 days
12.	Recommended fertilizer dose	300:150:150 NPK kg/ha
13.	Date of sowing	15/10/2024
14.	Date of transplanting	06/11/2024
15.	Period of picking	06/02/2024 to 28/03/2024

Tomato seedlings (Syngenta Saaho) were transplanted on 06 November 2023 in a double row with spacing of 90 cm x 60 cm on ridge.

Irrigation and Fertigation management

Before transplanting, to bring the soil at the field capacity in each plot common irrigation was given on 06 November 2023. Considering the use of polyethylene mulch, which saves about 20 % of irrigation water (Deshmukh, 2015), the water requirement of tomato crop under drip irrigation at 80 % ET_c (crop evapotranspiration) was worked out using modified Penman Monteith model (eq.3.1). The successive first irrigation was given on 08th November 2023 and then irrigation was applied every day. FAO Penman Monteith equation is expressed as:

where,

$$ET_o = \frac{0.408 \Delta (R_n - G) + \gamma \frac{900}{T+273} u_2 (e_s - e_a)}{\Delta + \gamma(1+0.34u_2)} \quad \text{----- (3.1)}$$

- ET_o : Reference evapotranspiration, mm day⁻¹
 R_n : Net radiation at the crop surface, MJ m⁻² day⁻¹
 G : Soil heat flux density, MJ m⁻² day⁻¹
 T : Air temperature at 2 m height, °C
 U₂ : Wind speed at 2 m height, m s⁻¹
 e_s : saturation vapour pressure (kPa)
 e_a : actual vapour pressure (kPa)
 Δ : slope vapour pressure curve (kPa °C⁻¹)
 γ : psychometric constant (kPa °C⁻¹)

The values of crop coefficient used for different growth stages of tomato crop are referred from FAO 56. The crop evapotranspiration values for tomato crop is calculated by using following formula.

$$ET_c = K_c \times ET_o$$

where,

ET_c = crop evapotranspiration (mm d⁻¹)

K_c = crop coefficient (dimensionless)

ET_o = reference crop evapotranspiration (mm d⁻¹)

Table Effect of fertigation levels on WUE for tomato production

Treatments	Irrigation Water applied, mm	Yield of tomato, q/ha	WUE
T1	576	124.28	0.22

Irrigation scheduling

To achieve optimal and efficient production, irrigation for the tomato crop was scheduled every day.

Fertigation scheduling

The recommended fertilizer dose of 300:150:150 N:P:K kg/ha was considered. In treatments T₁ to T₄, water soluble fertilizers (source - 19:19:19 WSF complex and urea) through drip fertigation was applied in 12 splits at an interval of 10 days.

In control treatment T₅, soil application of basal dose of 50% N + 100% P + 100% K (sources – Urea, SSP, and MOP) were given as conventional fertilization through drip fertigation at the time of transplanting and remaining 50% of N (source-Urea) was given through drip fertigation.

Water Use Efficiency

The first harvesting is done after the sixty days of transplanting when the fruits were fully developed and turned yellow to reddish colour. Further pickings were done at an interval of ten days. The yield of tomato from net plot in every treatment was observed in every picking. The total yield of the fruit harvested from net plot was recorded by cumulating yield per picking and expressed in kg per plot and then it is converted into quintal per hectare.

Using yield recorded and irrigation water applied, water use efficiency was calculated using following relationship.

$$WUE = \frac{\text{Total Tomato production, q/ha}}{\text{Total irrigation water applied, mm}}$$

Results and Discussion

Based on yield recorded and irrigation water applied WUE was calculated and presented in following table and depicted in Fig. 1.

T2	576	131.42	0.23
T3	576	132.57	0.23
T4	576	155.71	0.27
T5	576	114.28	0.20

Fig. 1 Variation of water use efficiency

The highest yield was observed in Treatment T₅ while lowest was recorded in treatment T₅. All drip fertigation treatment showed higher tomato yield than that obtained in treatment T₅ (Traditional fertilization at 100% RDF). Similar trend was found in case of water use efficiency. Therefore, it is suggested to implement treatment T₄ (drip fertigation with 120% of RDF) for more tomato yield.

References

1. **Ayyar, S. (2019)**. Mulching and fertigation on the yield and quality of tomato. *IJCS*, 7(4), 2539-2541.
2. **Amit Saurabh, 2 Manish Kumar, 2018**, Effect Of Different Training Systems, Spacings And Fertigation Levels Interactions (2 Way) On Yield Contributing Attributes In Bell Pepper Under Protected Conditions In Mid Hills Of Himachal Pradesh, VOL. VIII, ISSUE XXVII, OCT 2018 *Multilogic In Science* ISSN 2277-7601
3. **Deshmukh P. V. (2015)**. Response of tomato to polyethylene mulch under drip fertigation, Unpublished thesis, Dr.PDKV, Akola
4. **Fabio Favati, Stella Lovelli, Fernanda Galgan and Vito Miccolis (2009)**. Processing tomato quality as affected by irrigation scheduling. *Scientia Horticulture*, 122: 562-571.
5. **J.M. Patel1 , N. G. Savani2 , B. M. Solia3 And K. K. Patel4, 2022**, Response Of Cabbage To Different Discharge Rates, Fertigation Levels And Lateral Placements, VOL. XII, ISSUE XXXXI, Jan 2022 *Multilogic In Science* ISSN 2277-7601, Page 192-195
6. **Kaushal, S., Kumar, V., & Sharma, S. (2021)**. Effect of tomato hybrids to different growing media and fertigation on soil properties under naturally ventilated polyhouse. *Canadian Journal of Agricultural and Applied Sciences* *CJAAS* 1(1): 25-29

7. **Mahadeen Atif Y (2014)**. Effect of polyethylene black plastic mulch on growth and two summer vegetable crops under rain-fed conditions under semi-arid region conditions. *American Journal of Agricultural and Biological Sciences* 9 (2): 202-207
8. **Michael, A.M. 1974**. Irrigation Engineering: Theory and Practice. Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi: 457
9. **Navatha. N1 , Madavi. B2 , Madhukar Rao. P3 , Raju. B4 , Umareddy. R, 2020**, Effect Of Fertigation Levels And Frequencies On Growth And Yield Of Maize In Sandy Loam Soil, VOL. IX, ISSUE XXXII, JAN 2020, *Multilogic In Science* ISSN 2277-7601, Page 426-432.
10. **P. S. Wankhede S. D. Dahiwalkar, V. R. Mandave, 2018**, Effect Of Irrigation And Fertigation Levels On Spectral Signature Of Tomato Crop Over Its Crop Growth Period And Relate Ndvi With Crop Coefficients Under Polyhouse Conditions, VOL. VIII, ISSUE XXVII, OCT 2018 *Multilogic In Science* ISSN 2277-7601, Page 74-77.
11. **V. D. Tayade1 , A. M. Sonkamble2 , P. K. Nagre3 , V. S. Kale4 , S. B. Wadatkar5 , R. D. Walke 2024**, Effect Of Irrigation And Fertigation Levels On Yield And Economics Of Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* Thunb.) VOL. XIII, ISSUE XXXXVII, July 2023 *Multilogic In Science* ISSN 2277-7601, Page 950-956.
12. **Vedika Sharma1 , Amit Saurabh*2, Ruksana3 , Diksha Saini4 , Himanshi5 and Pallvi Sharma 2023**, Effect Of Different Hybrids And Fertigation Levels On Benefit Cost Ratio Of Cucumber (*Cucumis Sativus* L.) Under Poly House Conditions, VOL. XIII, ISSUE XXXXVI, April 2023 *Multilogic In Science* ISSN 2277-7601, Page 640-642.